

On quantitative relations

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To obtain clear mutual relations within phenomenological reality we have to perform measurements. For example the difference in mass between different types of particles. But these measurements have only a reliable meaning in relation to an “absolute” background. Because if we don’t know “what is going on” we cannot categorise the mutual properties of the phenomena in a reliable way. So how do we get reasonable insight into relational reality?

Introduction

We can imagine a universe without matter (a primordial universe). That means that the universe was in a state of total vacuum space. This is possible if the universal scalar field – the Higgs field – is perfectly flat everywhere in the universe. If we use the model of quantised space^[1] to examine this state it shows that the universal electric field is not flat because every unit of quantised space changes the shape of its unit with the same amount of topological deformation. The latter is responsible for the generation of corresponding vectors within the flat Higgs field (the vectors of the magnetic field).

The “power” behind the continues deformation of the shape of the units of quantised space is the internal spherical shape forming mechanism (short: scalar mechanism). Every unit of quantised space has identical basic properties (invariant volume, deformable, internal scalar mechanism). And last but not least the units of quantised space tessellate the volume of the universe. In other words, the units of quantised space *are* the volume of the universe.

If we want to obtain clear mutual relations within phenomenological reality with the help of the model of quantised space we have to figure out which relations are significant and which are not.

References:

1. S.E. Grimm (2024); “On the geometrical structure of quantised space”.

<https://zenodo.org/record/14556269>

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The primordial universe

The units of quantised space deform constantly and synchronously because of their internal scalar mechanism. However, every unit shares its surface area with its adjacent units. So it is easy to conclude that the total amount of shared surface area of all the units of quantised space is a constant. That means that the sum of all the local changes of shared surface area (A) must be zero ($\sum \Delta A = 0$).

The schematic figure 1 shows in cross section a linear topological deformation under invariant volume between 3 units in vacuum space. To simplify the explanation I have drawn the deformed parts of the units as cubes. The unit at the right hand has pushed the deformed part of the unit in the centre to the left (green arrow). If the focus is on the unit in the centre the green arrow represents input deformation (1) and the red arrow represents output deformation (2). The volume of every unit is equal and invariant, thus the sum of all the *internal* transfer of volume (V) of all the individual units of quantised space is zero ($\sum \Delta V = 0$).

figure 1

If we think about the consequences of the deformation of the shape of a unit of quantised space under $\sum \Delta A = 0$ and $\sum \Delta V = 0$ it is clear that in the primordial universe change is equal to the amount of asymmetry of the shape of every unit. We can express the “power” behind all the changes in the universe by the scalar mechanism with the help of the known constants that represent the energy of the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field. Because the linear propagation of the quantum of energy (h) is the constant speed of light (c). Moreover, all the changes in quantised space are synchronised because the volume of every unit is equal and invariant. Thus change has a metric.

The pass on of the fixed topological deformation across the volume of 1 unit (ℓ_c) determines the constant of quantum

time ($t_q \times c = \ell_c$). The size of 1 unit of quantised space (ℓ_c) is about $0,5 \times 10^{-15}$ m. It can be derived with the help of the measured radius of a proton (about $0,73 \times 10^{-15}$ m).^[2] Because a proton is a composite particle with a spin. That means that the diameter of a proton cannot be smaller than 3 units in line. Now it is easy to calculate the duration of the constant of quantum time (about $5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second).

The image (cross section) in figure 1 also shows that the increase/decrease of the joint surface area of a unit in vacuum space is equal to the increase/decrease of the surface area of the scalar (1) that is part of the boundary of the unit. It in contrast with our ideas about the deformation of an object in phenomenological reality.

figure 2

Figure 2 shows the principle of topological deformation under invariant volume (reference 1, page 3). The topological deformation of a unit is the result of an input deformation from adjacent units and an output deformation towards other adjacent units. This means that the *internal* flow of volume of every unit that results in a change of its shape is the result of $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$. The Planck constant (h) represents a full cycle – input and output – so if we want to determine the amount of energy, generated by the scalar mechanism of *one* unit, we have to split the Planck constant ($\frac{1}{2} h$). In other words, the amount of change of every unit during the constant of quantum time (t_q) is $\frac{1}{2} h$.

If we talk about energy (E) in physics it is about the energy of $E = h f$ (Planck) and the energy of $E = m c^2$ (Einstein). But the energy of $E = h f$ is a manifestation of the “power” to change a fixed amount of topological deformation in relation to a certain duration and constant velocity, while $E = m c^2$ is about the imaginary transformation of “free” energy into a local concentration of energy (m).

Both expressions of the nature of energy describe phenomena (electromagnetic waves and matter). But if we want to express the “power” of the scalar mechanism of each unit of quantised space in the primordial universe we are limited to a description of the changes of the surface area

(boundary) of a unit or a description of the distribution of the internal transfer of volume within the boundary of a unit. That means that we specify $\Sigma \Delta V = 0$ into $\Sigma \Delta V_1 + \Delta V_2 + \Delta V_3 + \dots + \Delta V_{12} = 0$. Because every unit has 12 adjacent units in vacuum space.

The consequence of the changes of the universal electric field and its corresponding magnetic field (together termed electromagnetic field) in the primordial universe is the existence of electromagnetic “amplitudes” everywhere in the universe. These amplitudes are compositions of topological deformation and are the source of mutual relations that are manifested as *probability distributions*.^[3]

Unfortunately, every amplitude – actually an energy density – generates corresponding vectors within the flat Higgs field. These changing vectors during $1t_q$ don’t influence vacuum space around with the speed of light. Vectors act instantaneous. Figure 3 represents a bit more realistic image of a unit (schematic as a rhombic dodecahedron), the topological deformation at the joint faces (schematic blue bi-directional arrows) and the vectors of the magnetic field (black) within the points of contact of the scalar (grey) of the unit with the not drawn adjacent scalars..

figure 3

Figure 1 shows the influence of the topological deformation of the units on the symmetry of the shape of the units around. Figure 3 shows the relation between the topological deformation of a joint face and the change of the generated magnitudes of the vectors of the magnetic field by the topological deformation of the joint faces.

So if we imagine an amplitude of the electromagnetic field in vacuum space – actually an amplitude of energy density – the amplitude represents energy and corresponding vectors (the magnetic field). The vectors are in the outward direction so these vectors will spread the energy accumulation (the amplitude). Actually keeping the Higgs field flat.

References:

2. T. Cai et al. (2023), “Measurement of the axial vector form factor from antineutrino-proton scattering” Nature 614, 48-53 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05478-3>
3. S.E. Grimm (2021); “The mechanism behind probability” <https://zenodo.org/records/5515861>

Decreased scalars

The fundamental difference between the condition of the basic quantum fields in the primordial universe and our present state of the universe is the existence of matter (m). Local concentrations of energy that are stable in relation to their “enclosed” amount of concentrated energy ($E = m c^2$). The differences between the amplitudes of the electric field in the primordial universe and the existence of local concentrations of energy in the present universe are local changes of the magnitude of the scalars of the universal scalar field (Higgs field).

The diagram in figure 4 shows the resistance against deformation of a unit of quantised space.^[4] In the primordial universe every scalar of the Higgs field has an identical radius ($r_{is} = 1,0$). If we imagine the existence of a solitary unit – that means a unit without adjacent units around – the shape of this unit is a sphere and its radius $r_{is} = 1,105$. Because the volume of the inscribed sphere (scalar) in vacuum space is related to the whole volume of the unit as 74% to 100%.

The diagram only shows the undistorted scalar mechanism of the unit. The resistance against deformation of the deformed part of the unit is unknown because it has not the shape of a sphere. Unfortunately that is not the only problem to determine the strength of the deformed volume of an element.

figure 4

If a rest mass carrying particle is created ($E = m c^2$) the energy of the mass originate from the average energy “density” of vacuum space around. The consequence is that the creation of matter in the universe results in a decrease of the average energy density in vacuum space. We can argue that this amount of energy of the particle is negligible in relation to the whole volume of vacuum space. However our universe evolves in a balanced way. That means that the total amount of energy of matter is in a dynamic equilibrium with the energy density in vacuum space around.

figure 5

Figure 5 shows a spiral galaxy. Around the galaxy I have drawn in a schematic way some influences that have created the galaxy. The black arrows symbolize the push of the scalar mechanism of every unit of quantised space to increase their symmetry. In the primordial universe the average energy density was so high that the concentration of topological deformation resulted in the emergence of black holes and the directly related force of gravity (blue arrows). Below a certain amount of energy density in vacuum space there is not enough energy to create new black holes. But there is still enough energy to continue the creation of rest mass carrying particles. Because a black hole is just an enormous rest mass carrying particle.^[5]

The consequence of the dynamical balance is that it is difficult to get reliable quantitative relations in a universe with a universal scalar field that isn’t flat any more. Although it is easy to conclude that the total magnitude of the generated vectors is equal to the resistance against deformation of the scalar mechanism of a unit in vacuum space (see figure 3; $r_{is} = 1,0$).

The law of conservation of energy is a confirmation of the conservation of energy transfer in the primordial universe. It means that all the vectors in the primordial universe are also conserved because the universal electric field and the magnetic field are corresponding fields.

In other words, if every unit of quantised space changes its shape with a topological deformation of $\frac{1}{2}h$ during the constant of quantum time ($1t_q = 5,99 \times 10^{-23}$ second), every unit generates vectors (F) with corresponding magnitudes. So I can write $\sum \Delta F = 0$. In other words, the vectorisation of vacuum space by decreased scalars of the Higgs field is just a manifestation within the conservation of vectors.

References:

4. S.E. Grimm (2019); "On the concept of (quantum) fields" <https://zenodo.org/records/3585790>
5. S.E. Grimm (2024); "On resultant motion in discrete space" <https://zenodo.org/records/11193931>

Decreased scalars

In physics a particle is a local concentration of energy. That means that within a certain volume of vacuum space, energy as a certain amount of available topological deformation, have been concentrated. If the concentration of energy doesn't force a scalar in the centre to decrease its radius ($r_{is} = 1,0$) the concentration of energy is comparable with a local energy amplitude in vacuum space. However, at the moment a scalar in the centre decreases its radius the scalar forces a vectorisation of the flat Higgs field around the scalar. Vectors that point in the direction of the scalar.

figure 5

Figure 5 shows a particle in vacuum space. The red dotted circle (A) – a hypothetical spherical volume – symbolises the amount of involved units that have transferred a part of

their surplus of topological deformation towards the centre of the vol-um. An amount of energy that is just enough to pass the threshold that is needed to change the radius of the scalar in the centre of the concentration. The black dotted line represents the whole volume that has contributed to the mass of the particle.

The diagram in figure 6 shows the increase of topological deformation at the joint face between 2 adjacent units. It is just a calculation to examine the relations between the surface area of the deformed part of one unit (light grey) and the amount of surface area of the scalar that is "forced" to be part of the boundary of the adjacent unit (dark grey).

The diagram doesn't represent what is exactly going on, it only shows that after the threshold (I) of decreasing the radius of the scalar has passed, a further internal transfer of volume – from I to II – doesn't increase the amount of surface area in the joint face. Actually it decreases a bit. That means that point II acts as a type of energy well (state of stability).

figure 6

The vectorisation of the flat scalar field around the particle represents the origin of the gravitational force (Newtonian gravity as a push force from vacuum space around).^{[6][7]} Because a further increase of the energy of the particle will not increase the amount of vectorisation of the flat Higgs field by the decreased scalar because the vectorisation represents a scalar mechanism "resistance" of $r_{is} = 1,0$. However, the average energy density in vacuum state evolves during the creation of matter in the universe. So what will be the effect of this decrease?

The involved volume to concentrate energy and forces the scalar to decrease its radius – see figure 5; the dotted red circle – is not fixed. It cannot have a constant size because it depends on the average energy density in vacuum space.

An energy density that reflects the average topological deformation of the units of quantised space. Like the black dotted line (B) in figure 5 symbolises the additional number of units that can pass on topological deformation towards the particle, because of the decreased scalar (point II, figure 6).

The image below (figure 7) shows in a schematic way a decreased scalar (red), the adjacent units (black) and the generated vectors within the flat Higgs field around (red arrows). The concentric circles (grey) represent the increasing topological deformation under influence of the generated vectors.

However, all the units of quantised space (squares) deform synchronously their shape with $\frac{1}{2} h$ during every $1 t_q$ (constant of quantum time). That means that the red vectors are super positioned on the vectors of the magnetic field. It also means that the decreased scalar is passing on its energy (topological deformation) in relation to the structure of quantised space.

figure 7

But the pass on (motion) of this huge amount of energy in relation to the rest frame is not the speed of light. Its velocity is related to its amount of energy because of the synchronisation and quantisation of the topological deformation of every unit. In other words, if the energy concentration has passed to the adjacent units during $\Delta t = 10^{20} t_q$, all the other units in vacuum space have also exchanged topological deformation 10^{20} times.

Figure 8 shows in a schematic way the same particle and generated vectors by the decreased scalar in the centre. But the concentrated topological deformation of the particle is in motion in the direction of the vertical black arrows.

figure 8

The consequence is that the concentrated energy of the particle forces the units in vacuum space to transform their shapes in correspondence with the moving particle. That is why a part of the vectors (black arrows) of the magnetic field manifest themselves as a dipole.^[8] Observers will interpret the dipole as an external influence that is part of the properties of the particle.

Because all the units of quantised space transform their shape constantly and synchronously it is clear that the universe transforms in a state of dynamic equilibrium (like the non-locality of a self generating fractal). But particles are creations in relational reality. So we cannot express the quantitative relations between composite phenomena in terms of the basic properties of quantised space (the rest frame). The consequence is that the radii of the dotted circles A and B in figure 5 are not fixed, they evolve.

References:

6. S.E. Grimm (2019); “On quantum gravity”
<https://zenodo.org/records/3590404>
7. S.E. Grimm (2019); “On curved spacetime”
<https://zenodo.org/records/3596008>
8. S.E. Grimm (2025); “The dipole in quantised space”
<https://zenodo.org/records/14630170>